

Chemistry Teacher Interest: A Crucial Factor in Chemistry Education and Development in Nigeria

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Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to highlight interest as an element of development and its consequence on teacher education and development. This opinion paper considers students' interest in teaching as a profession despite the positive enrollment statistics, so as to contribute and stimulate debate and discussion, and offer new perspective and insights. Literature review and expert opinions methods were used to support the author's opinion. Results were synthesized to support the author's opinion on interest and its benefits to chemistry teacher education and development, factors responsible for students lack of interest on teaching discussed into; the country's poor educational system, mini salaries/remuneration, desire to get money quick, love for soft work, discouraging testimonies from teachers/educators in the system, lack of prestige associated with the profession, and lack of models. The consequences have negative effect on teacher's education and development in general and chemistry teacher's education and development in particular which has resulted to production of graduates with education certificate but without interest in the profession. Ways to improve and sustain students' interest were recommended. However, if the recommendations are implemented, it will move teachers from lamentation stage to the stage of influence.

Keywords: Chemistry, interest, teacher education, development

Introduction

Chemistry as a science, studies the properties and behaviour of matter, forms of matter and the transformations they undergo, the energy that is released or absorbed as a result of these transformation processes, the chemical combination laws of matter and how the knowledge of the properties of matter can be used to provide and sustain the need of the society in solving and sustaining societal problems. According to Anne (2020), Chemistry is a major contributor to the development of every other sector of human endeavours. It is not an understatement that consciously or unconsciously we perform chemical reaction every day considering that everything we do involve chemistry underpins and sustained the important of chemistry. Even our body metabolism is controlled by chemicals which include our breath, urination, sweating and other activities. All matter is made of chemicals, and chemistry studies the chemical components of matter, so by studying the chemical components of matter it shows the importance of chemistry as the study of everything since everything that exist are matter. Students wanting to become doctors, nurses, physicists, nutritionists, geologists, pharmacists, and (of course) chemists all study chemistry is a prerequisite for study of medicine, nursing, physics, nutrition science, geology and mining, pharmacy, and (of course) chemistry. There are lots of job opportunity for people that study chemistry.

Chemistry education is a study of how to teach chemistry, also known as chemical education, is based on studying and learning chemistry. Potential chemistry teachers are to study the fundamental principles of chemistry with teaching methods and strategies, Chemistry education focuses on efficient teaching method, and with teaching aids for better understanding chemistry. This is in line with chemeurope.com(2024), which recorded that Chemistry education is a dynamic field of study that spans both chemistry and education disciplines. Researchers in this area investigate how students learn chemistry and how instructors can teach it more effectively in various educational settings, from primary schools to higher education institutions. The ultimate goals are to enhance students' understanding of chemistry, refine teaching methods, and improve learning outcomes. To achieve this, instructors need ongoing training and support to stay updated on best practices, which can be applied through diverse teaching approaches, including lectures, demonstrations, and hands-on laboratory experiences.

A teacher plays a vital role in creating a nurturing and inclusive learning environment in the educational journey of students that empowers students to reach their full potential. By inspiring critical thinking, creativity, and curiosity, teachers foster academic excellence, social growth, and emotional development. Their key responsibilities include designing engaging lessons, assessing student progress, providing constructive feedback, and guiding students towards their academic goals. To stay effective, teachers must stay updated on curriculum developments and best practices, collaborate with colleagues and parents, and continuously develop their skills. As mentors, role models, and knowledge facilitators, teachers have a profound impact on students' lives and shape the future generation. To excel in their roles, teachers require ongoing education and development that is engaging and relevant.

Teacher Education

Teacher education or teacher training refers to programs, policies, procedures, and provision designed to equip (prospective) teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours, approaches, methodologies and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community. The professionals who engage in training the prospective teachers are called teacher educators (or, in some contexts, teacher trainers). Teacher education is the bedrock of quality education. It ensures that educators are enriched with the expected skills, seasoned knowledge, and pedagogical techniques to effectively engage students and facilitate meaningful learning experiences. Teachmint(2024), explained teacher education as a vital component of any educational system, providing a comprehensive training program that prepares candidates with the necessary skills, knowledge, and attitudes to excel in teaching.

Through this programme, aspiring teachers learn effective instructional strategies, develop essential competencies, and cultivate positive behaviours to create a supportive learning environment. Teacher education empowers educators to foster student learning, address diverse needs, and adapt to the ever-changing landscape of education, ensuring they stay updated on best practices and innovative teaching methods. Without proper training, and with the problems facing teachers' education in Nigeria such as; poor budgeting/ funding resulting to brain-drain, lack of seasoned lecturers, inadequate and dilapidated infrastructural facilities, ineffective supervision to maintain standard, strike actions, and little or no capacity development, the quality of education suffers and has resulted to lack of interest in both teachers and prospective teacher's.

Interest as a Factor

Interest is the sine qua non for teacher education and development in general and to chemistry teacher education and development in particular because without interest, development is like ocean without water, it will be a

venture heading to extinction. Harackiewicz, Smith, and Priniski (2016), extensively discussed the importance of interest in their work titles: *Interest Matters: The Importance of Promoting Interest in Education*. According to them, interest plays a crucial role in driving learning, shaping academic and career paths, and achieving academic success. It encompasses both a temporary emotional response to a subject and a long-lasting inclination to revisit it. The four-phase model of interest development offers a framework for strategies that foster interest and build on existing ones.

Four effective approaches to boosting interest include: capturing attention through engaging environments, leveraging individual interests, using problem-based learning, and highlighting practical applications. By cultivating interest, educators can create a more immersive, motivating, and effective learning experience for students. Hence, students' interest of becoming a teacher is an important element of teacher education and development because, it benefits both the teacher and the profession. For teachers, Student interest is a crucial factor in teacher education and development because it:

1. Motivates teachers to create engaging lessons
2. Encourages teachers to use innovative teaching methods
3. Helps teachers understand student learning styles
4. Increases teacher enthusiasm and passion for teaching
5. Enhances teacher-student relationships
6. Improves student participation and engagement
7. Boosts student confidence and self-esteem
8. Increases student achievement and academic success
9. Encourages teachers to stay updated on new teaching methods
10. Fosters a positive and supportive learning environment

By considering student interest, teachers can shape their instruction precisely to an extent to meet the diverse educational needs and abilities of their students, fostering a more effective democratic and enjoyable learning experience. This, however, nurtures and sustains the ongoing education and development of teachers as educators because such is attainable through self-development. However, building students' interest in a subject can indeed influence them to consider teaching as a career because of the following:

1. Passion breeds passion: When students are passionate about a subject, they may want to share that passion with others, leading them to consider teaching profession.
2. Role models matter: Students may be inspired by their own teachers who made the subject engaging and fun, and aspire to emulate them.
3. Sense of purpose: When students are interested in a subject, they may feel a sense of purpose in sharing their knowledge with others, leading them to consider teaching career.
4. Developing expertise: As students delve deeper into a subject, they may want to continue learning and sharing their expertise with others, making teaching a natural fit.
5. Making a difference: Students may realize that teaching allows them to make a positive impact on future generations, motivating them to pursue a teaching career.
6. Building confidence: When students are interested in a subject, they may feel more confident in their abilities, making them more likely to consider teaching as a career.

7. Exposure to teaching experiences: Providing students with opportunities to assist in teaching or lead workshops can help them develop a taste for teaching and build their confidence.

8. Mentorship: Having a mentor or role model in the teaching profession can foster learner's interest to consider teaching as a career.

By fostering students' interest in a subject, we can inspire and motivate them to see teaching as a fulfilling job, perpetuating a cycle of passion and expertise. An extract of Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board admitted candidate statistics by state and faculty, 2018, which shows that faculty of Education has the second largest population of admitted candidates of 89,617, is not true expression of interest if factors that influenced the candidates choice is considered, such as; referral factor, inability of the candidate to get the requirements to study course of choice among others.

a) Referral factor: Referral impose factors such as sponsorship condition and peer competitive factor can make student settle for chemistry education. Sponsored programs may come with conditions so students may feel obligated to pursue Chemistry Education due to sponsorship rather than personal interest and parents who are in education sector with the opportunity to bring in their children into the sector can pressure or influence their children to study chemistry education. Also when students are competing with their peers, seeing their peers secure admission and going ahead of them may make them settle for chemistry education so as to get admission like their peers.

b) Eligibility factor: In Nigeria, eligibility criteria for University admission can pressure students into settling for Chemistry Education, even if it is not their preferred choice. For instance, strict admission requirements and limited slots in popular courses like Medicine, Engineering, among others make students to opt for Chemistry Education as a safer alternative. Also, Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) subject combination and West African Senior School Certificate Examination subject requirements can limit and influence students' choices. Chemistry Education might be seen as the only viable option for students who want to study science-related courses.

Therefore, is clear that despite the benefits of interest the issue of lack of interest in the teaching profession persists especially it regards chemistry education.

Lack of Interest in Teaching Profession

Interest is the sine qua non for teacher education and development in general and to chemistry teacher education and development in particular, hence the foundation of teacher education and development is based on solid and sustained interest because, without a prospective teacher, there will be no teacher to educate and develop. Oyeleke (2022) captured 6 reasons youths lack interest in the teaching profession:

1. The state of the educational system in the country

The condition of the national educational system especially the institution of learning owned by the government is worrisome. The national educational system is characterised by various crises such as poorly equipped and dilapidated infrastructure, waste of resources, poor conditions of service, and so on. All these are a strong contributor that discourages Nigerian youths from considering the teaching profession as a good and reliable career for one who wants to be successful in life.

2. Discouraging remuneration

Considering their enormous contribution, teachers should be well paid due to the great and delicate role they perform for different sectors of society through the life of every child trained, discouragingly, they are among the

poorly remunerated comparing them with workers in other sectors in this part of the world, confirming the belief in this part of the world that no one can pay for the real worth of a teacher and that their reward will be in the afterlife. This belief is also applicable in the medical field, but they are among the well-paid workers in the world. Hence, teachers be remunerated just like those in the medical field.

3. Quick money syndrome

This generation which is characterized by the desire to get money quickly and become financially stable at a young age, has built a strong culture of disbelieving in hard work around youths who will rather prefer quick means to become wealthy by cutting corners.

An individual's passion and love to impart knowledge is the driving force for the teaching profession, money is a secondary factor as regards to teaching profession. However, the youths of this generation are passionate about quick money, this has greatly contributed to the decline in youths' interest in the teaching profession.

4. Love for 'soft' work

The teaching profession is sustained by passion because it is tasking, this has made the teaching work uninteresting to youths of this generation who are no longer interested in any job that is demanding. They prefer "soft" work, a job with little or no stress with yet a good income. Hence, a decline of interest in the teaching profession is anticipated as it is a job that's demanding and stressful at times.

5. Discouraging testimonies from professional teachers

There are cases in which some teachers have consciously or unconsciously discouraged young people who have a passion for teaching from the profession. There are cases where a teacher continually talks to students about going into lucrative career paths rather than following their passion because of the teacher's own experience or a teacher who constantly complains of the poor condition of service or poor remuneration before the students. This is enough reason for anyone not to go into the profession despite the passion as they would rather choose to learn from their teachers' experience rather than experiencing this themselves.

6. Lack of professional prestige

The nonchalant attitude of the government to the academic staff, poor remuneration, and the crumbling state of the nation's educational system, are all factors that contribute to the decline in the prestige of the teaching profession. Those in the education sector will rather advise one to go into other viable options than teaching. Hence, teaching profession has become one that is daily experiencing a reduction in its prestige as a result.

Lack of interest is a huge clog to teacher education and development and it's quite unfortunate that a profession contributing to all sectors of society is gradually losing its prestige and relevance in society. However, the teaching profession remains a king profession irrespective of youths' decline of interest. Hence, for those who have an interest in impacting knowledge to others the problem of prestige shouldn't stop you go for self-development because as a teacher you are a nation builder, and building a nation requires self-development.

Teacher's Self Development

A teacher's self-development is the fruit of built and sustained interest, when students interest motivates teachers to create engaging lessons, encourages teachers to use innovative teaching methods, helps teachers understand student learning styles, increases teacher enthusiasm and passion for teaching to mention but a few, it will make the teacher to go for self-development in other to bring such benefits to fruition. However, teacher self-development especially Chemistry teacher self-development should be holistic as emotional intelligence is central knowing that emotion contributes to how the brain functions. This is supported by Zineb (2023) who opined that

occurring of these aspects of development: personal, professional, and social development can be taken as Teacher development. It is important to note that these aspects of development are possible through teacher's self-development programs such as workshops, in-class observation, and seminars.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The vehicle that will drive this profession into extinction is a lack of interest if not addressed. This paper addresses the course element of teacher education and development which is building and sustaining interest through system Hybridization/collaboration. System hybridization refers to the sharing of resources, in this case, human resources (teachers), between universities and secondary schools to achieve a common goal: leveraging modeling to build and sustain interest in chemistry education which involves:

- 1. Teacher sharing:** Universities and secondary schools partner to share teachers, expertise, and resources.
- 2. Modeling:** Teachers from universities model effective teaching methods, share research-based practices, and demonstrate innovative approaches to teaching chemistry.
- 3. Capacity building:** Secondary school teachers learn from university teachers, enhancing their own skills and knowledge in chemistry education.
- 4. Collaborative teaching:** University and secondary school teachers co-teach, plan lessons, and develop curriculum materials together.
- 5. Mentorship:** University teachers mentor secondary school teachers, providing guidance and support.
- 6. Professional development:** Teachers from both institutions participate in joint professional development programs, workshops, and conferences.

By system hybridization, universities and secondary schools can leverage each other's strengths to build and sustain interest in chemistry education, ultimately benefiting students and the broader education community through:

- 1. Improved teaching quality:** Shared expertise and resources enhance teaching quality in both universities and secondary schools.
- 2. Increased interest in chemistry:** Modeling and collaborative teaching spark students' interest in chemistry.
- 3. Sustained engagement:** Ongoing mentorship and support ensure continued engagement and motivation.
- 4. Capacity building:** Secondary school teachers become more confident and competent in teaching chemistry.
- 5. Stronger partnerships:** Universities and secondary schools develop stronger relationships, fostering a sense of community.

Therefore, this work explores interest as a factor in chemistry teachers' education and development considering its benefits to students, teachers and teaching profession, interest as regards to teaching profession were discussed and the following recommendations are advised:

- System Hybridization in terms of human resources sharing between secondary school Chemistry teachers and University lecturers to serve as models, which is in line with the Social learning theory of Albert Bandura, the psychologist, his work is based on learning through observation, imitation, and modeling.
- Effective use of classroom as wonderful instrument to influence and produce future political leaders that will solve the problem of poor educational system in the country is advised bearing in mind that teachers are nation builders.

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